

MAIN CAUSES AND MODERN TREATMENT OF BREAST CANCER

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ABSTRACT: In the article, significant information about causes and treatment of breast cancer were highlighted. On the other hand, the main factors of the disease and measures to prevent them are presented. The article uses the latest statistics on this disease.

Keywords: *therapy, medication, alcohol, benign breast conditions, a sedentary lifestyle, malignant, lining cells, tissue, surgery, radiation.*

We all have one life to live, and it is how we live it that makes all the difference, although this fact is only understood at a later stage in life. Good health makes us more lively, and life more exciting to go about. Healthy living is important to ensure that you live longer and live better. Every individual should make sure that they not only breathe but experience life and get the most out of it. Leading a robust life is, therefore, critical for every human being. When there is a change in our genes, cancer may happen. Now, not all cancerous cells are deadly. Some are benign while some are malignant. Breast cancer is a type of cancer that forms in your breasts. Asides from skin cancer, breast cancer is the most common cancer that affects women in the United States. Breast cancer can occur in men as well as women, but it is far more prevalent in women. It is possible to survive breast cancer once it's discovered on time. Learning about the common signs and symptoms plus ways to treat it can help in understanding the illness and

curing it. According to The U.S. breast cancer statistics, the average woman's breast cancer risk is about 13%, meaning about one in eight women will be diagnosed with invasive breast cancer in her lifetime. A man's risk is much lower, but about 1 in 833 men will get breast cancer in his lifetime. Everyone has some risk of developing breast cancer, but many factors can increase or decrease each person's breast cancer risk. Breast cancer arises in the lining cells (epithelium) of the ducts (85%) or lobules (15%) in the glandular tissue of the breast. Initially, the cancerous growth is confined to the duct or lobule ("in situ") where it generally causes no symptoms and has minimal potential for spread (metastasis). Over time, these in situ (stage 0) cancers may progress and invade the surrounding breast tissue (invasive breast cancer) then spread to the nearby lymph nodes (regional metastasis) or to other organs in the body (distant metastasis). If a woman dies from breast cancer, it is because of widespread metastasis. Breast cancer treatment can be highly effective, especially when the disease is identified early. Treatment of breast cancer often consists of a combination of surgical removal, radiation therapy and medication (hormonal therapy, chemotherapy and/or targeted biological therapy) to treat the microscopic cancer that has spread from the breast tumor through the blood. Such treatment, which can prevent cancer growth and spread, thereby saves lives.

Life habits (risk factors) you can control:

Alcohol use. Your risk for breast cancer may rise with every drink. Research suggests that women who drink one alcoholic beverage a day have a 7 to 10 percent increased risk for breast cancer compared with non-drinkers, and this number jumps to 20 percent for those who have two to three alcoholic drinks per day, according to the American Cancer Society.

Reduce your risk: For women, moderate drinking means no more than one drink per day. If you're a daily drinker, start by cutting back to just a few times a week. Also, become aware of how much you're drinking: A standard drink is about 14 grams of alcohol—that's 12 ounces of regular beer, 5 ounces of wine or

1.5 ounces of distilled spirits. If you're filling an oversized glass, that one drink could really count as two.

Your weight. Breast cancer is on the list of diseases and conditions caused or worsened by being overweight or obese after menopause. Your ovaries stop making the female sex hormone estrogen after menopause, so most estrogen comes from fat tissue. The more fat you have, the more estrogen you make, and estrogen feeds some breast cancers, causing them to grow. Women who are overweight also may have higher blood insulin levels, which have been linked to breast cancer and diabetes. Reduce your risk: Consider working with a dietitian to find a weight loss plan, one with lots of fruits and vegetables, that works for your lifestyle, making it more likely that you'll stick with it. Being at a healthy weight really helps. Women who lose weight after age 50 and keep it off have a lower risk of breast cancer than women whose weight stays the same. And the more weight you lose, the lower your risk. Women who lost about 4.4 to 10 pounds had a 13 percent lower risk than women who didn't lose weight, while those who lost 10 to 20 pounds had a 16 percent lower risk, and those who dropped more than 20 pounds had a 26 percent reduced risk of breast cancer, according to a large study in the Journal of the National Cancer Institute. Reduce the risk: Staying physically active may help decrease your chances of developing breast cancer and other diseases—and aid in weight-loss efforts. The American Cancer Society recommends that you aim for 150 to 300 minutes of moderate intensity exercise, such as brisk walking, or 75 to 150 minutes of more intense activity, like running, each week. The more physical activity you do, the greater the benefits. Get the all-clear from your doctor before making major changes to your exercise regimen. Benign breast conditions. Certain noncancerous breast conditions may confer a higher risk of developing breast cancer. The list includes proliferative lesions without cell abnormalities such as usual ductal hyperplasia, fibroadenomas, sclerosing adenosis, several papillomas and radial scars. Proliferative lesions with cell abnormalities, including atypical ductal hyperplasia

and atypical lobular hyperplasia, also increase risk. Women can reduce their risk of breast cancer by maintaining a healthy weight, reducing alcohol use, increasing physical activity, and breast-feeding. These modifications might prevent 38% of breast cancers in the US, 42% in the UK, 28% in Brazil, and 20% in China. The benefits with moderate exercise such as brisk walking are seen at all age groups including postmenopausal women. High levels of physical activity reduce the risk of breast cancer by about 14%. Strategies that encourage regular physical activity and reduce obesity could also have other benefits, such as reduced risks of cardiovascular disease and diabetes. A study that included data from 130,957 women of European ancestry found "strong evidence that greater levels of physical activity and less sedentary time are likely to reduce breast cancer risk, with results generally consistent across breast cancer subtypes". The American Cancer Society and the American Society of Clinical Oncology advised in 2016 that people should eat a diet high in vegetables, fruits, whole grains, and legumes. High intake of citrus fruit has been associated with a 10% reduction in the risk of breast cancer. Marine omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids appear to reduce the risk. High consumption of soy-based foods may reduce risk. Some treatments, like surgery and radiation, are local, meaning they treat the tumor without affecting the rest of the body. Most women with breast cancer will have some type of surgery to remove the tumor. Depending on the type of breast cancer and how advanced it is, you might need other types of treatment as well, either before or after surgery, or sometimes both. Drugs used to treat breast cancer are considered systemic therapies because they can reach cancer cells almost anywhere in the body. Some can be given by mouth, injected into a muscle, or put directly into the bloodstream. Depending on the type of breast cancer, different types of drug treatment might be used. Typically, treatment is based on the type of breast cancer and its stage. Other factors, including your overall health, menopause status, and personal preferences are also taken into account. Summing up all given facts, the most significant point in avoiding from any illness is living

in healthy life style. There are several benefits of a healthy life. Your body becomes free from various forms of disorders and thus, you get a longer life. You can live a life without suffering from any aches, pain, or discomfort. In every sphere of your life, you will be able to perform to the best of your ability. Doing excellent work helps you to be a valuable member of a healthy society. Besides, when you are physically fit, it gets reflected on your face. So, you look attractive and start feeling good about yourself! If you have a fit body, then you can lead a physically active life even after growing old. This is because, the body can heal the regular wear and tear associated with aging faster. In short, health and wellness brings about a drastic improvement in the overall quality of your life.

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